

Annual report CAA Netherlands-Flanders chapter (CAA-NLFL) 2018

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During the annual CAA meeting in Tübingen quite a lot of people from the CAA-NLFL chapter were present and contributed by presenting various papers or organizing sessions.

We have organized a day of workshops in cooperation with the Digital Archaeology Group from Leiden University on 26th of April (<http://www.caanfl.nl/?q=node/59>). The DAWN (Digital Archaeology Workshops Netherlands-Flanders) was as success. In total 39 people participated, about 2/3 academic (students and staff) and 1/3 from local governments or commercial companies. In the morning we organized two workshops (Image Based Modelling (IBM) and Archis (Dutch archaeological database from the State Agency)). In the afternoon we organized 3 workshops (IBM again, LiDAR and 3D-modelling). The workshops were sponsored by Leiden University and Archon (<http://www.archonline.nl/>). Following the success of the 2018 workshops, we are organizing a similar day of workshops in 2019 (<http://digarchgroup.nl/dawn/index.php>).

On the 4th and 5th of October we held our biennial Joint Meeting with CAA-DE (<http://www.caanfl.nl/?q=node/61>). The Meeting took place in Bochum in the House of Archaeologies in association with the German Mining Museum, Bochum Germany (Haus der Archäologien, Deutsches Bergbau-Museum, Bochum). The participants (67 registered in advance) were not only from Germany and the Netherlands, but also from Australia, Austria, Bulgaria, Italy, Sweden and Switzerland. The subjects of the papers were very varied, ranging from mining to ships, from 3D-documenting to data/text mining and from mobile apps to digitizing in 2 or 3 dimensions. There was ample time for fruitful discussion and this led to interesting insights for all. On the evening of the 4th nearly everyone ate together in Brauhaus Rietkötter, resulting in meeting new and old friends an important goal of the CAA. On the morning of the 5th, before the papers, a free tour through the Mining Museum was available.